

The Omic Image Format (OIF): A Unified Machine Learning–Native
Representation for Genomic and Epigenomic Data

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This dissertation is submitted for the degree of Master of
Philosophy
August 2025

Abstract

The function of a gene product is determined by two key layers of biological information: the genetic layer, encoded by the DNA molecule, and the epigenetic layer, which regulates the timing, location, and level of gene expression. DNA sequencing and methylation data provide complementary information in classifying disease onset, progression, and phenotypic variability. However, genomic and epigenomic data formats are not natively structured for direct use in deep learning, and there is no single representation which natively combines both genomic and epigenomic data in a biologically coherent and structured way. We present the Omic Image Format (OIF), a unified, machine-learning–native representation for genomic and epigenomic data, which encodes both nucleotide sequence and DNA methylation state into a spatially coherent image with associated metadata. To enable the adoption of the OIF, we developed and publicly released *OmicImage* (Abraham, 2025). This open-source, workflow-agnostic Python package converts coordinate-sorted SAM alignments and optional CpG methylation reports into OIF. Using the *Komagataella phaffii* reference genome, the OIF preserved 100% of the positional and compositional values across both genomic and epigenomic layers and over 99% agreement in methylation values after rounding tolerance. By aligning biological features with ML architecture requirements, the OIF and the *OmicImage* package provide a scalable, reproducible framework for multi-omic integration that has the potential to accelerate research, improve diagnostic workflows, and advance the integration of genomics and epigenomics into precision medicine.

Acknowledgements

When I arrived 11 months ago, it was with a limited understanding of clinical and molecular genetics. Now, I have developed a nuanced and expansive knowledge of the fundamental and cutting-edge biological and molecular mechanisms underlying genetics, along with a clear grasp of their biological foundations, clinical applications, aims, principles, challenges, and emerging frontiers in genomic medicine and healthcare. I am grateful for this understanding I have gained throughout the MPhil in Genomic Medicine. I suspect much of my future impact on the field will be traced back to this period, and to the passionate and exceptional professors and speakers whose instruction inspired and fostered in me, and peers, a deeper understanding and appreciation for the discipline. This includes Dr. Timothy Hearn, Prof. Serena Nik-Zainal, Prof. Miguel Constância, Dr. Leonardo Bottolo, Prof. Helen Firth, Prof. Giles Yeo, Dr. Gemma Chandratillake, Dr. Michael Quail, and Prof. George Vassiliou. Thanks are also due to Prof. Eamonn Maher and Dr. Marc Tischkowitz for both their teaching and their role in initiating and developing this program. I also deeply appreciate all those I have been unable to mention by name, but who, within this program, took the time to teach and inspire.

Sincere thanks to Daniel and Jennifer for their constant support and assistance in resolving issues whenever they arose.

Finally, I am grateful to those whose work I have read and cited, and which has ultimately contributed to the furthering of science in this and other fields.

Disclaimer

This dissertation does not exceed the maximum length permitted by the regulations for the MPhil in Genomic Medicine. No part of this thesis has been submitted for another qualification. It is the result of my own work and includes nothing which is the outcome of work done in collaboration except where specifically indicated in the text.

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Chapter 1 – Background and Literature Review

1.1 - The Genetic and Epigenetic Layer

The function of a gene product is determined by two key layers of biological information: the genetic layer, encoded by the DNA molecule, and the epigenetic layer, which regulates the timing, location, and level of gene expression.

1.1.1 - The Genetic Layer

The genetic layer, first described by Watson and Crick (1953), consists of two complementary nucleotide sequences in the form of strands, paired by base pairing. Each strand consists of a linear sequence of four nucleotide bases: A (adenine), T (thymine), C (cytosine), and G (guanine). Within this sequence lie four key regions which are critical to genome function.

Exonic protein-coding elements, which are directly involved in protein synthesis, were shown by Berget et al. (1977) and Chow et al. (1977) to be interrupted by non-coding introns through the discovery of split genes and mRNA splicing. Thus, establishing how the coding regions of eukaryotic genes were separated by non-coding introns, which are spliced to form functional mRNA.

Regulatory elements, which control the spatial and temporal expression of genes, were characterised in foundational studies by Jacob and Monod (1961) in prokaryotic operons, and later extended to eukaryotic enhancers and transcriptional activators by Banerji et al. (1981) and Levine and Tjian (2003), who established that gene expression was not determined solely by coding sequence, but also by regulatory regions which respond to developmental and environmental cues.

Intronic non-coding regions, which are often transcribed into RNA, were first discovered by Berget et al. (1977) and Chow et al. (1977) through the discovery of introns within eukaryotic genes, where they found that protein-coding regions in eukaryotic genes are interrupted by non-coding sequences. Demonstrating that some non-coding sequences have essential roles in processing RNA and gene regulation.

Structural and repetitive elements, which contribute to genome stability and chromosomal integrity, were identified and characterised through the identification of centromeric DNA (Clarke and Carbon, 1980), telomeric repeats (Blackburn et al., 1978), and highly repetitive sequences dispersed throughout the genome (Britten and Kohne, 1968)

Collectively, these four key regions of the genetic layer are critical to the function of an organism. They define the ability of the genome to encode, regulate, and preserve genetic information, which forms the molecular basis for gene products to be produced, controlled, and maintained.

1.1.2 - The Epigenetic Layer

The epigenetic layer comprises a set of biochemical modifications to the DNA molecule and its associated histone proteins, which regulate the expression of a gene without modifying the underlying nucleotide sequence. These modifications affect the resulting gene product by influencing when, where, and how much a gene is expressed. Within the epigenetic layer, there are three distinct types of epigenetic modifications: DNA methylation, histone modification and chromatin remodelling. The two most studied are DNA methylation and Histone modification.

DNA methylation, which involves the addition of methyl groups to cytosine molecules at CpG sites in a nucleotide sequence, was first described by Hotchkiss (1948), where studies of calf thymus DNA showed that cytosine modification was a naturally occurring modification. Additional oxidised derivatives of 5-methylcytosine (5mC), such as 5-hydroxymethylcytosine (5hmC), were identified by Kriaucionis and Heintz (2009), where studies of Purkinje neurons revealed a distinct derivative in DNA methylation. Ito et al. (2011) later identified 5-formylcytosine (5fC) and 5-carboxylcytosine (5caC) during investigations of TET enzyme activity, which showed that the modifications were intermediates in active DNA demethylation pathways.

Histone modifications, which refer to post-translational chemical changes of histone proteins, play a key role in regulating chromatin structure and gene expression. These

modifications were first linked to gene transcription by Allfrey, Faulkner, and Mirsky (1964), who observed that histone acetylation was associated with gene activation. Subsequent studies identified further histone modification, such as histone methyltransferases (HMTs) identified by Rea et al. (2000) and Bannister. et al. (2001), histone phosphorylation identified by Mahadevan, et al. (1991), who demonstrated how H3 phosphorylation is involved in chromatin remodeling during mitosis, and histone ubiquitination, identified by Briggs et al. (2002), who identified the role of H2B ubiquitination in promoting H3K4 and H3K79 methylation.

1.2 - Genomic and Epigenomic Data – Biomarkers in Disease

Diagnosis

1.2.1 - The Role of DNA Variants in Disease Diagnosis

DNA sequencing is routinely used to support the diagnosis of both Mendelian and complex diseases by identifying pathogenic variants which are associated with specific clinical phenotypes (Koboldt et al., 2013; Richards et al., 2015). For example, *IDH1* and *IDH2* variants in glial cells are used to confirm the diagnosis of diffuse gliomas (Louis et al., 2021; Riemenschneider et al., 2010). Repeat expansions in *HTT* and *DMPK* support the diagnosis of Huntington's disease and myotonic dystrophy (Caron, Wright and Hayden, 2018; Bastepe and Xin, 2015; Seifert et al., 2024; Peric et al., 2021). *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* variants are used to confirm a diagnosis of hereditary breast and ovarian cancer syndromes. *CFTR* variants are used to diagnose cystic fibrosis, particularly in newborn screening programs and those with clinical phenotypes (McGarry et al., 2022), illustrating how genomic variant detection is central to diagnosing genetic disease.

Despite their use in disease diagnosis, DNA variants do not fully account for disease onset and progression (Kingdom and Wright, 2022). The manifestation of pathogenic variants also depends on the mutation context, genetic background, and gene-environment interaction (Virolainen et al., 2022; Otwinowski, McCandlish and Plotkin, 2018; Ciesielski et al., 2024). Furthermore, Rausell et al. (2014) and Wang et al. (2022) demonstrated how some frameshift mutations are tolerated if they occur outside functionally critical domains, leading to misleading classifications if context is ignored. Variant-only approaches also struggle with somatic mosaicism due to standard Sanger sequencing failing to detect pathogenic alleles with allele fractions below 15–20% (Chen et al., 2014; Netto et al., 2021), which can result in misdiagnosis, especially in condition characterised by variable tissue expression, and low-level mosaicism (Richards et al., 2015).

Moreover, variant analysis does not capture insight into the regulatory activity of the nucleotide sequence. This limitation can lead to misguided diagnosis, as a gene may appear

structurally intact, yet its expression is silenced as a result of epigenetic mechanisms such as DNA methylation or histone modification (Esteller, 2007; Jones and Baylin, 2016). This diagnostic limitation is particularly evident in imprinting disorders, where epigenetic dysregulation accounts for approximately 50% of cases, and in cancers, where epigenetic modifications such as promoter hypermethylation and global hypomethylation often contribute to disease onset and progression. (Feinberg, 2007; Sharma et al., 2022).

Consequently, reliance on DNA sequence alone risks both false negatives and false positives, which undermine diagnosis accuracy (Richards et al., 2015). Addressing this limitation, recent studies have demonstrated how the integration of epigenetic information supports accurate and improved disease diagnostic models. For example, Füllgrabe et al. (2023), using a six-letter sequencing method that simultaneously reads genetic variants and DNA methylation from blood samples, found that combined methylation–genetic models improved mortality prediction compared to DNA sequence-only models, showing that epigenetic data as a diagnostic and prognostic tool complements genetic-only approaches.

Supporting this, Sadikovic et al. (2021) performed genome-wide methylation profiling in over 200 individuals with suspected neurodevelopmental disorders, among cases which were unresolved by DNA sequencing methylation sequencing enabled a definitive diagnosis in 27.6% of cases, including 35.3% in individuals with previously inconclusive genetic findings, demonstrating how methylation-based testing can solve the diagnostic ambiguity especially in cases when nucleotide sequence data is inconclusive.

1.2.2 - DNA Methylation as an Epigenetic Biomarker in Disease

Epigenetic modifications contribute to human diseases and disorders. Among these, DNA methylation is the most studied and plays a critical role in regulating gene expression, maintaining the stability of the organism's genome and regulating the expression levels of gene products. DNA methylation is an epigenetic mechanism which involves the addition of a methyl group to the 5th carbon of the cytosine nucleotide base, typically within CpG sites. This process is catalysed by DNA methyltransferases, which are a conserved family of cytosine methylases with a key role in epigenetic regulation (Lyko, 2018).

The functional impact of DNA methylation is dependent on the genomic context in which it occurs. In particular, there are several key mechanisms through which DNA methylation regulates gene expression and genomic stability.

Promoter region methylation was demonstrated by Bird (1986) and Hendrich and Bird (1998), who used methylation-sensitive restriction enzymes to study CpG island methylation, and found that methylated CpG islands inhibited transcription factor binding and promoted the recruitment of repressive chromatin modifiers, which resulted in gene silencing.

Gene body methylation was described by Zilberman et al. (2007), who, in conducting and comparing methylation patterns from genome-wide DNA methylation profiling of *Arabidopsis thaliana* and other mammals, found that gene body methylation was positively correlated with the expression of the gene, showing how the methylation of a gene body promotes the transcriptional activity of a gene.

Global hypomethylation and genome instability was first described by Feinberg and Vogelstein (1983) who in performing high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) and methylation-sensitive Southern blotting to compare the DNA methylation levels of normal and colorectal cancer tissues discovered increased hypomethylation in repetitive elements and non-coding regions in tumor DNA relative to normal tissue, demonstrating that global hypomethylation is an early and common occurrence in tumorigenesis.

Imprinting control region methylation and monoallelic parent-of-origin expression was first described by Surani, Barton and Norris (1984), and later Reik et al. (1987), who in modifying methylation marks in imprinting control regions (ICRs) in mouse models found that methylation on the paternal allele of the *H19/Igf2* locus silences *H19* and activates *Igf2*, while unmethylated maternal alleles allow *H19* expression and suppress *Igf2*. Additionally, they noted that loss of the methylation marks resulted in biallelic expression and developmental abnormalities, showing how methylation at imprinting control regions is essential in establishing parent-of-origin-specific gene expression.

1.2.3 - Diagnostic Utility of DNA Methylation Profiles

DNA methylation provides stable, tissue-specific, and persistent methylation patterns across disease states, which serve as reliable molecular signatures that aid in disease diagnosis, particularly in cases where DNA sequencing or other modalities, such as histology analysis, result in inconclusive findings. These molecular features make DNA methylation profiling a valuable tool to complement conventional diagnostic methods.

For example, Rakyan et al. (2011) used *Illumina* Infinium 450K methylation arrays to profile DNA methylation patterns in human tissues affected by diseases such as cancer and diabetes. They found diseased tissues exhibited distinct and consistent methylation signatures. Additionally, they found tissue-specific methylation signatures in blood samples, even when DNA sequence data appeared structurally sound, highlighting the identification and persistence of methylation patterns in various disease types.

Additionally, in genomic imprinting, Rosenski et al. (2025), utilising WGBS to analyse the methylation profiles across 39 human cell types, identified differentially methylated regions (DMR) as hallmarks of both known and novel imprinted genes. Furthermore, Woodfine, Huddleston, and Murrell (2011) developed and validated 50 quantitative DNA assays targeting known DMRs associated with human imprinted genes and demonstrated that the methylation patterns were stable across adult tissue, further supporting how methylation patterns persist and are detectable through adulthood.

Filippidou et al. (2024), performing a study on children and adolescents with central nervous system (CNS) tumours, demonstrated how methylation profiling on the tumours confirmed 86.5% of cases, refined 48% of cases into subtypes, and changed the diagnosis for 9.6% of individuals with incorrect diagnoses. This included two new diagnoses in patients with non-conclusive histopathology, demonstrating the diagnostic value of methylation profiling in supporting disease classification. Similarly, Moran et al. (2016) developed a DNA-based methylation classifier to predict the tumour type in 261 cases of cancer of unknown primary. The classifier correctly identified the primary cancer in 87% of the cohort, enabling diagnosis and tumour-specific therapy, resulting in a reduced risk of death by 67%, compared to

patients who received non-targeted treatment for their cancer subtype and had a hazard ratio of 3.24.

Collectively, these examples demonstrate how DNA methylation patterns in conditions such as imprinting disorders persist and provide stable, disease-specific signatures that support the diagnosis and guide the prognosis across a range of conditions. However, the clinical utility of methylation integration depends on careful assay selection and the contextual interpretation in order to ensure methylation-based insights support clinical outcomes.

1.2.4 - Limitations of Epigenetic Sequencing in Clinical Contexts

Despite its clinical utility, epigenetic sequencing, particularly bisulfite-based methods, presents several limitations. Meissner et al. (2005) developed Reduced Representation Bisulfite Sequencing (RRBS) to selectively target regions enriched with high CpG content, particularly promoters and CpG islands; however, this results in sparse genome-wide coverage in CpG sites outside of these regions, such as low CpG content gene bodies, enhancers, and intergenic regions.

Nunn et al. (2022) assessed the variant calling accuracy on BS-Seq data with and without masking and found that without preprocessing, BS-Seq data produced poor variant calling accuracy making the DNA sequencing unreliable for clinical-grade mutation detection, this is because Bisulfite sequencing converts unmethylated cytosines to thymines making it difficult to identify true C>T mutations from converted nucleotide bases, which renders mutational analysis unreliable when using DNA derived from methylation sequence for variant analysis.

Furthermore, Miller et al. (2023) analysed promoter methylation profiles from thousands of human tissue samples and found that DNA methylation is highly tissue-specific, which can result in reduced diagnostic accuracy, especially in cases where, due to tissue inaccessibility, the sample tissue is not the primary site of the disease.

Finally, Kalari and Pfeifer (2011), comparing methylation patterns across early-stage and malignant tumours using mouse models and human samples, found that some methylation

events, such as early *Foxd3* hypermethylation, preceded tumorigenesis in cancer development, whilst other changes, such as promoter methylation in non-developmental genes, occurred later. This highlights the challenge in distinguishing causative driver methylation changes from passenger methylation changes, as not all methylation changes are functionally relevant or causative to the disease phenotype.

These examples highlight that whilst epigenetic characterisation is a valuable tool in understanding disease, particularly in cancers and imprinting disorders, it must be interpreted within a broader biological and environmental context to accurately assess disease risk and presentation.

1.2.5 - The Complementarity of Genetic and Epigenetic Information

DNA sequencing and methylation data provide complementary information in classifying disease onset, progression, and phenotypic variability. However, whilst DNA variants help identify inherited and somatic mutations which increase the likelihood of disease occurrence, they do not capture the regulatory dynamics which drive genes to be silenced or expressed (Füllgrabe et al., 2023). Conversely, DNA methylation sequencing identifies cell and tissue-specific regulatory activity but cannot detect pathogenic variants in the DNA sequence (Loyfer et al., 2023; Villicaña and Bell, 2021). Thus, relying on either method in isolation from the other risks diagnostic oversight, especially in disease phenotypes where both genetic and epigenetic mechanisms can contribute to a shared phenotype (Suter, Martin, and Ward, 2004; Cohen et al., 2018).

For example, in Lynch syndrome, a hereditary disease which predisposes individuals to cancers including colorectal and endometrial cancers, microsatellite instability (MSI) and loss of mismatch repair (MMR) protein function often arise from germline mutations in the MMR genes *MLH1*, *MSH2*, *MSH6*, *PMS2* (Peltomäki, 2016). However, the same MSI phenotype, which results from deficient MMR protein function and is observed in many sporadic colorectal and endometrial cancers, can occur due to epigenetic silencing of the *MLH1* gene through promoter hypermethylation (Herman et al., 1998; Esteller et al., 1998).

Therefore, whilst the phenotype (MSI-high/MMR-deficient) looks similar in both hereditary and sporadic tumours, the underlying cause, and thus the clinical implications, are very different. Additionally, approximately 80% of MSI/dMMR tumors are sporadic (Leclerc et al., 2021), meaning that using only DNA sequencing would result in false positives for Lynch syndrome (Gausachs et al., 2012), in addition to misguided family screening in patients; conversely, solely using information from methylation profiling would result in false positives as a result of overlooking germline mutations entirely.

Therefore, the accurate classification of many diseases depends on the utilisation of both DNA sequencing and methylation sequencing for accurate diagnosis, risk assessment, and clinical decision-making, requiring a unified approach which combines both DNA and epigenetic mechanisms for analysis.

1.3 - Data Generation and Storage: From Sequencing to Format

1.3.1 - Sequencing Workflows: Genomic vs. Methylation-Based Approaches

DNA and methylation sequencing are used to capture different features of DNA. DNA sequencing aims to capture the precise order of nucleotides which form DNA. In contrast, DNA methylation sequencing aims to capture methylation signatures at CpG sites, which regulate gene expression without altering the DNA sequence.

The difference in the targeted molecular feature by the two sequencing types results in distinct methods of sample preparation and sequencing technologies.

For example, in DNA sequencing, DNA is first extracted, fragmented, and prepared into a sequencing library. This library is then processed using platforms such as *Illumina*, *PacBio*, or *Oxford Nanopore* (Hess et al. 2020).

Similarly, in DNA methylation sequencing, DNA is first extracted, fragmented, and prepared into a sequencing library; however, additional library preparation is added, such as sodium bisulfite treatment or enzymatic methyl-seq. Bisulfite treatment results in conversion of unmethylated cytosines to uracil (Simons et al., 2025), whereas enzymatic methyl-seq uses enzymes to distinguish methylated from unmethylated cytosines. These modifications allow for the detection of the methylation status at CpG sites.

These sequencing workflows reflect the unique layers of biological insights that can be derived from the sequencing of DNA. Whilst DNA sequence identifies the nucleotide layer, methylation sequencing captures the layer of regulatory control. Furthermore, the differences in the molecular target, library preparation, and computational tools contribute to the structural separation of genomic and epigenomic information. This issue has significant implications for data integration and downstream analysis.

1.3.2 - File Formats in Genomic Sequencing Workflows

Across the genomic and methylation sequencing workflows, file formats serve as the medium which provides the structural representations that store and encode the unique features of each biological layer. These formats not only define how the biological layer is computationally stored but also limit its interpretability across sequencing types. Three key file formats are most commonly used within the genomic workflow: FASTQ, BAM and VCF. Each format plays a distinctive role in genomic analysis, supporting the flow and processing of genomic data in genomic analysis pipelines.

1.3.2.1 - FASTQ

Cock et al. (2009) define the Sanger FASTQ standard for the FASTQ format, which is a human-readable plain-text format which stores the raw nucleotide sequence reads and their associated base quality score. Each read of a nucleotide sequence is represented over four lines: a header line which begins with @, a nucleotide sequence from the sequencing run, the + operator and the quality score. The quality scores are typically Phred+33 encoded ASCII characters, which represent the confidence of the nucleotide base being correct.

1.3.2.2 - SAM and BAM

Li et al. (2009) introduced the Sequenced Alignment Map (SAM) format, a human-readable format which is used to store nucleotide sequence reads that have been aligned to a reference genome. They also introduced the Binary Alignment Map (BAM) format, which is a compressed, binary version of the SAM format designed for efficient storage and indexing. The SAM format consists of two sections: the header section, which contains metadata about the file, including the sequencing data it holds, and the alignment section, which consists of records which correspond to one nucleotide read. Sections of the alignment read include: QNAME, which stores the unique identifier for the read, the FLAG field, which stores a bitwise flag indicating read property information such as if the read is paired or

mapped, and the MAPQ field, which provides a mapping quality score indicating the confidence of the alignment.

1.3.2.3 - VCF

Danecek et al. (2011) introduced Variant Call Format (VCF), which is a tab-delimited text format used to store the output of variant calling and consists of genomic variants that have been identified during the alignment process. The VCF Specification v4.2 (Samtools, 2024) defines the format as comprising a metadata section, a header, and data lines. Each data line records a variant and key information such as its chromosomal position, the reference and alternate nucleotide sequence, and quality scores, which indicate the confidence of the variant call.

Collectively, these genomic file formats enable modularity and interoperability across the genomic analysis pipeline, which supports reproducibility from raw nucleotide sequencing reads to variant identification.

1.3.3 - Specialised File Formats in Methylation Sequencing Workflows

The consistency and widespread standardisation of genomic file formats contrast against the file formats used in methylation sequencing. Methylation sequencing workflows often rely on a set of specialised, fragmented formats which vary depending on the sequencing platform and the stage of methylation analysis. Additionally, these files are often more tool-specific and are designed to capture methylation information at various levels of resolution. Formats include: IDAT, methylation-aware BAM, and CpG methylation reports.

1.3.3.1 - IDAT

IDAT is a proprietary format used to store raw signal intensities from *Illumina* methylation arrays such as the 450K and *EPIC* platforms. Each binary file contains fluorescence intensity measurements for each probe across red and green channels, in addition to metadata across the sample (Aryee et al., , 2014; illumina, 2025). Each intensity value reflects how strongly a

probe binds to its corresponding CpG site in the sample and is used to calculate methylation levels.

1.3.3.2 - Methylation - aware BAM

Methylation-aware BAM files are standard BAM formats that include additional optional tags which encode the cytosine methylation status at single-base resolution. These optional tags are produced by bisulfite sequencing aligners such as *Bismark v0.23* (Krueger and Andrews, 2011) or *BS-Seeker* (Guo et al., 2013). Additional flags include `XM` (methylation string), `XR` (read conversion), and `XG` (genome strand). Although methylation-aware BAM files follow the BAM format specification and can be indexed, they are not fully interoperable with standard genomic BAM workflows and require specialised tools for their interpretation.

1.3.3.3 - CpG Methylation Reports

CpG methylation reports are detailed, text-based files which summarise methylation information for individual cytosines across a sample. They are generated by tools such as *Bismark v0.23* (Krueger and Andrews, 2011) or *MethPipe v5.0.1* (Song et al., 2013) to capture methylation information at single-base resolution. The report includes fields which store the records of cytosine, such as chromosome, genomic coordinate, strand and the number of methylated and unmethylated reads.

While these formats enable the capture of DNA methylation at various levels of resolution, their tool-specific and often proprietary nature, along with the lack of standardisation across aligners, limit interoperability and complicate integration with broader genomic workflows.

1.3.4 - File Format Fragmentation: Structural Barriers to Multi-Omic Analysis

The structural separation of both genomic and epigenomic information poses a significant barrier to multi-omic analysis and the effectiveness of computational pipelines.

As discussed in section 3.2, nucleotide reads and methylation data are stored in distinct file formats. These formats have been developed independently of each other, optimised for sequencing type and analytical modularity rather than a unified representation of genomic and epigenomic information. These groupings allow for the interpretability between each domain but not amongst the unique sequencing types. For example, FASTQ files are aligned to generate SAM/BAM files, and in some cases, SAM or BAM files can be converted back to create FASTQ files using external tools such as *bedtools* v2.31.1 `bamtofastq` (Quinlan and Hall, 2010) and *samtools* v1.22.1 `fastq` (Danecek et al., 2021). Both the SAM and FASTQ files can then be used in separate pipelines to create a VCF file. Conversely, a CpG methylation report can be created from an IDAT file using external tools such as *minfi* v3.21 (Aryee et al., 2014), *SeSAMe* v3.21 (Zhou et al., 2018), or *ChAMP* v2.20.1 (Tian et al., 2017); however, since the fragmentation of genomic and epigenomic formats results in the omission of biological data, it is not possible to create a VCF or FASTQ file from an IDAT file or CpG methylation report.

The incompatibility between the data formats makes joint modelling and multi-omic analysis challenging. Hayes et al. (2024) conducted a review into multi-omics, highlighting how the incompatibility between coordinate systems and file structures acts as a bottleneck by limiting integrated bioinformatic analysis.

Duan et al. (2021) performed a comparative evaluation on various data integration strategies for cancer subtyping using genomics and epigenomics. They found that integration performance is limited by the incompatible data formats, particularly the genomic VCF and epigenetics IDAT file, which often requires custom ad hoc processing to link these datasets.

Furthermore, because the resulting methylation and genetic information are generated from distinct biological sequencing types and stored in incompatible formats, they often differ in base-level nucleotide resolution and coverage depth, or unified metadata, demonstrated by Chen et al. (2020) who noted that misalignments with coordinate system and the resolution of sequencing and metadata standard significantly impeded integrating genomic data in multi-omic studies.

This modularity and incompatibility of data formats result in siloed bioinformatics components and architecture, which necessitates extensive preprocessing before joint modelling can be attempted (Duan et al., 2021; Hayes et al., 2024). This not only introduces noise, data loss, and technological complexity and requirements, but also reduces the robustness of machine learning applications and bioinformatic reproducibility.

Additionally, although the genomic file formats provide the granularity needed for downstream genomic and methylation analysis, there is no universal standard for column formatting or metadata annotation. This has led to the existence of many file formats with differing structures across tools. As a result, integration with broader genomic analysis workflows often requires custom preprocessing and conversion steps, limiting interoperability and scalability across institutions and methylation pipeline types.

Thus, the current structural separation of genomic and epigenomic data is more than a technical inconvenience that has resulted from unique sequencing aims but a design flaw which reduces biological insights, hampers integrated modelling, and limits the translational utility of multi-omic data in clinical settings.

1.4 - Machine Learning in Biomedicine

1.4.1 - Why Machine Learning Matters in Genomics

The previous chapters established the genomic and epigenetic formats and the biological, clinical, and computational importance of integrating both genetic and epigenetic information for accurate disease and phenotype classification. Furthermore, these structured segmentations of bioinformatic pipelines and data formats not only limit bioinformatic interpretability but also the translational utility of multi-omic data.

Most importantly, whilst the format incompatibility results in technical inefficiencies across pipelines, the consequence is most pronounced in the context of machine learning, which is increasingly becoming a fundamental component in computational genomics. Similar to current bioinformatic tools, ML applications have strict structural requirements on input data, such as the requirement of numerical, tensor-compatible input structures with consistent size and alignment across samples. Thus, current genomic and methylation formats such as VCF, BAM, and IDAT are not merely inefficient but, without extensive preprocessing, are fundamentally incompatible with the data architectures required by ML workflows and serve as barriers to ML scalability, reproducibility, and the accuracy of diagnostic analysis.

The following section describes the role of ML in biomedical analysis, outlining the key data requirements and assumptions ML models make about the input data, and then demonstrates how current genomic data formats do not fulfil these assumptions or requirements. In doing so, it aims to highlight the need for a new format for genomic data representation, not solely for the improvement of bioinformatic pipeline integration but for compatibility with machine learning itself.

1.4.2 - What is Machine Learning

Machine learning is a field of study concerned with the development of statistical tools and algorithms that enable computational systems to improve their performance on specific

tasks, typically by identifying features and patterns in data and experience without explicit programming.

For example, ML models have been created to identify cancer subtypes from gene expression data (Mayur Divate et al., 2022) and detect diabetic retinopathy from retinal images (Gulshan,, 2016). Additionally, in fields that generate data characterised by high dimensionality, complexity, and often noisy datasets, such as genomics, biomedical imaging, and electronic health records, machine learning has been a key tool for accelerating clinical discovery, diagnostics, and treatment planning (Rajkomar et al., 2019).

The learning process consists of models which extract statistical regularities that are characteristic of the data, which the model then uses to make predictions, perform classification tasks, and highlight statistically significant features (Hinton, Vinyals, and Dean, 2015).

Unlike traditional programming and statistical methods, which require that explicit instructions are defined for each case, machine learning systems learn statistical patterns and representations from data, which allow them to make generalisations from data, enabling the performance of tasks without manual rule-coding (Goliarz et al., 2025). This adaptability to various types of data is particularly useful in domains where the relationships that characterise the input data and resulting outcomes, such as in medical images, are complex, probabilistic, and poorly understood (Rueckert and Schnabel, 2019).

Thus, by applying ML techniques to complex and often large-scale data, ML models can uncover characteristics and insights that are often missed by rule-based programs and statistical techniques (Barragán-Montero et al., 2021). The key feature of ML that has led to its increasing use has been its capacity to support a range of learning methodologies, which allow researchers to tailor specific paradigms to align with the data and goals of the task. Among these various methodologies and paradigms, the most common is deep learning, which has been transformative in extending the capabilities of machine learning.

1.4.3 - The Emergence of Deep Learning

Deep learning is a subset of ML that utilises artificial neural networks (ANNs) to model statistically significant patterns and features in data. The multi-layered structure of ANNs means that initial early layers are used to learn low-level features, whilst deeper layers capture more abstract high-level representations (LeCun, Bengio and Hinton, 2015). This hierarchical structure makes deep learning suitable for modelling data in domains that are characterised by unstructured or high-dimensional data, such as images, text, and biological data.

For example, Esteva et al. (2017) demonstrated this strength of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) in detecting malignant skin lesions from clinical photographs, with accuracy rates comparable to board-certified dermatologists, highlighting the diagnostic ability of deep learning in medical imaging analysis. Zhou and Troyanskaya (2015) developed DeepSEA, a deep learning model which, using one-hot encoded genomic sequences, was able to predict the regulatory effects of non-coding DNA variants, including estimating the impact of single-nucleotide variants (SNVs) on gene regulation across cell types, demonstrating how regulatory function could be derived from DNA segments.

Unlike traditional ML models, which rely on manual feature labelling and extraction, deep learning models can learn from raw data. The multi-layered architecture of ANNs enables deep learning models to identify features and relationships that commonly used statistical methods and shallow ML models may miss (Alzubaidi et al., 2021; LeCun, Bengio and Hinton, 2015). The ability to learn directly from raw, unstructured data is advantageous for use in genomics, where the biological mechanisms underlying the data are often complex or partially understood.

However, recent theoretical work has challenged the assumption that deep networks inherently learn novel representations. Domingos (2020) argued that in certain conditions, deep neural networks trained via gradient descent are mathematically equivalent to a kernel machine. In this view, instead of discovering new features, deep neural networks interpolate predictions by reweighting the gradients from the training data.

This reinterpretation of deep learning implies that the performance of deep learning models depends less on their architecture, but instead more on how well the input data represents biological features. It underscores the importance of accurate data representation, especially in domains with complex and non-standard formats.

1.4.4 - Learning Paradigms in ML and Their Biomedical Application

Across the various ML pipelines, deep learning has evolved to become a key framework through which ML paradigms learn from data. There are four key paradigms: supervised learning, unsupervised learning, reinforcement learning, and self-supervised learning, which offer unique methods for identifying patterns and making predictions, supporting multi-modal applications in bioinformatics, personalised medicine, and clinical support systems.

For example, in supervised learning, Golub et al. (1999) used ML to classify subtypes of leukaemia from gene expression data, demonstrating early success in genomics-based diagnosis. In unsupervised learning, the Human Cell Atlas employed cluster-based methods on single-cell RNA sequencing data to identify previously unknown cell types (Xie et al., 2021).

In the original AlphaFold, Senior et al. (2019) used reinforcement learning techniques to guide protein structure prediction from amino acid sequences. Their findings demonstrated that reinforcement learning could help predict the conformations of protein molecules. This enabled the development of AlphaFold2 (Jumper et al., 2021), which used supervised learning to predict the structures of over 210,000 proteins.

In self-supervised learning, Rives et al. (2021) trained the ESM-1b transformer model on over 250 million protein sequences. Despite being trained without functional labels, the model was able to learn sequence representations that captured secondary and tertiary structure, in addition to mutational effects of variants, outperforming traditional alignment-based methods in downstream tasks, including remote homology detection and the prediction of variant effects.

Each paradigm addresses objectives and constraints that result from data: where supervised learning requires data that has been labelled in order to provide direct prediction, unsupervised learning operates solely on unlabeled data, aiming to identify inherent structure (Alzubaidi et al., 2021). Reinforcement learning learns from data generated through environmental interactions, where learning is optimised based on reward functions (Sutton and Barto, 2018). Self-supervised learning uses raw and unlabeled data to create labels through sub-tasks, which allow the model to learn statistically significant features from the structure of the data itself (Chen et al., 2019). Together, these paradigms highlight the flexibility of ML methodologies and their capacity to address a range of biological questions from disease classification to biomolecular understanding.

1.5 - Data Constraints and the Need for Format Alignment in Deep Learning

1.5.1 - Deep Learning Input Constraints Across Domains

Deep learning (DL) has emerged as a transformative approach to solving complex problems and achieving defined aims in a range of fields. However, its effectiveness is dependent on the type and quality of the input it receives. For DL models to perform effectively, the input data must meet structural and domain-specific requirements, ensuring alignment both to the architecture of the model and the characteristics of the problem. There are multiple established data constraints, such as Numerical Representation and Fixed Input Dimensions (Goodfellow et al., 2016; Krizhevsky et al., 2012; Vaswani et al., 2017), which apply to over eight domains, including computer vision and natural language processing. Together, these constraints define the data requirements that must be satisfied for the efficient performance of deep learning models.

For example, in computer vision Krizhevsky et al. (2012) adhering to deep learning data constraints such as ensuring all image inputs were converted into numerical tensors, resized to a fixed dimension of 224×224 pixels, and normalised to have zero mean and unit variance achieved a top-5 error rate of 15.3% on the ImageNet classification benchmark far outperforming traditional approaches to image classification, demonstrating how strict adherence to deep learning data requirements in computer vision tasks supports effective model performance.

Supporting this, Dodge and Karam (2017) deliberately introduced visual distortions such as blur, Gaussian noise, and image misalignment to CNN input data, thus breaking the assumptions of fixed input integrity, batch consistency, and semantic preservation. This deliberate violation of key input constraints resulted in accuracy drops of up to 30% across multiple CNN architectures, underscoring the fact that deep learning models perform poorly when input data deviates from the expected data structure.

In using tabular data, Borisov et al. (2022) highlight that deep learning models underperformed when raw categorical variants and unprocessed data violated key data constraints such as numerical encoding and normalisation. When the data was modified to meet at least one of these constraints (numerical encoding), the performance improved, highlighting the fact that DL underperforms in domains where the native data format does not align with the structural requirements of neural architectures.

These findings reflect a broader principle: DL models, such as convolutional neural networks, are designed to process information that is numerical (Vaswani et al., 2017), fixed in size (He et al., 2014), and spatially structured (Liu et al., 2018). Additionally, because models do not have functions to natively transform misaligned data to native representations, even small deviations from the expected data constraints such as normalisation or numerical representations results in reduced and often inadequate model performance, thus highlighting, the fact that DL performance is reliant on the degree to which the input data satisfies the core architecture constraints on the ML model.

1.5.2 - Why Deep Learning Excels in Medical Imaging

Machine learning, particularly deep learning, has had a transformative impact in medical imaging fields such as radiology, dermatology, and histopathology. However, these breakthroughs are attributable not only to advances in model architecture but also to the use of formats that natively meet the requirements set by the DL architecture to which the images have been applied.

For example, medical images consist of densely encoded, two-dimensional arrays of pixel values, where each pixel is defined numerically, often with greyscale intensities or multi-channel values. Values are normalised, and the format is anchored spatially to represent data. Additionally, the images used for models are shaped consistently across samples. These properties are directly utilised by tensor-based input requirements of convolutional neural networks (CNNs), which rely on local spatial relationships for model performance (Krizhevsky et al., 2012; Litjens et al., 2017).

Furthermore, success in medical imaging applications has been supported by format standardisation such as DICOM, which, by formalising image standards including the preservation of data resolution, metadata, and coordinate values, has ensured that image-based data is naturally compatible with DL models, which enable effective model performance, wider academic reproducibility, and large-scale model generalisation.

Overall, this alignment in the structure of data input and the model constraints enables ML models to effectively generalise across cell types and image features, resulting in success in medical image analysis using DL.

1.5.3 - Why Genomics Underperforms in Deep Learning Pipelines

In contrast, genomic and epigenomic data formats are not natively compatible with machine learning pipelines. The formats are characterised by symbolic, fragmented, and irregular line-separated data which do not align with the data constraints set by various DL architectures.

For example, the structure of the standard genomic data formats, including FASTQ and SAM, consists of multiple lines, each holding a specific type of information. Raw DNA reads are encoded as a linear string of A, T, C, and G, while quality scores are stored separately as ASCII characters. Unlike image formats, these representations lack numerical encoding, positional anchoring, and spatial continuity, which are features required for ML models to learn effectively (Stephens et al., 2015; Li et al., 2009).

Similarly, epigenetic data, namely DNA methylation data, is stored as non-numerical values, with CpG in separate rows for CpG sites and methylation percentage. This results in a data separation which does not meet DL data representation requirements. Additionally, the separation between the DNA and methylation formats means there is no consistent schema or coordinate system for integration. This structural separation leads to inconsistent feature dimensions, unmatched resolution, and disjoint sample mappings, resulting in the inability of architectures to construct unified input tensors suitable for end-to-end ML training (Ballard et al., 2024).

This misalignment of data requirements hinders the feasibility of performing ML experiments with genomic data. In the absence of a native ML format, researchers are forced to implement custom, task-specific preprocessing pipelines, adding computational overhead and introducing variability, which reduces reproducibility and limits scalability across datasets and studies (Samuel, Löffler and König-Ries, 2020; Han, 2025).

This highlights that the core bottleneck is not the architecture of ML models, but the representation of genomic data. While machine learning excels in structured domains like imaging, the lack of native genomic formats that align with DL model architectures results in reduced use in ML without task-specific solutions.

1.5.4 - Exceptions That Prove the Rule: When Genomics Works in ML

Despite these challenges with native data formats, successes with genomics-based tools such as *AlphaFold* and *DeepSEA* suggest that this format gap can be bridged to result in novel outcomes. The following section explores how ML successes in genomics have all required one key step: the creation of bespoke data formats in order to adhere to the constraints of the DL model.

To overcome the limitation of a lack of native ML formats in genomics, successes in ML and genomics have all required the creation of bespoke data formats, which have enabled the performance of these experiments.

For example, AlphaFold (Jumper et al., 2021), which has been able to predict the 3D structure of over 214 million proteins from amino acid sequence, relied on the creation of bespoke evolutionary-derived alignments and spatial contact maps, which transformed the symbolic amino acid sequences into numerical tensors with built-in spatial semantics. The formats were additionally explicitly crafted to encode positional relationships and structural constraints, instead of relying on the raw sequencing strings of the original format, showing how the raw format was transformed to meet the constraints of the deep learning model.

Similarly, DeepSEA (Zhou and Troyanskaya, 2015) and Enformer (Avsec et al., 2021) reformatted 4 million raw DNA sequences using a bespoke, densely featured, fixed-length numerical matrix, where each position encoded sequence context, including regulatory features and cell-type-specific data, showing how a bespoke ML-native format was used over raw FASTA and VCF files in order to train an ML model to predict the functional consequences of variants, enhancer-promoter interactions, and chromatin states.

Furthermore, in self-supervised learning, the ESM-1b model (Rives et al., 2021) relied on protein sequences, which were tokenised, embedded, and processed via masked prediction to meet the DL constraints instead of raw nucleotide sequences, which allowed the model to extract key information such as secondary and tertiary protein structure and functional motifs. This resulted in performance improvements on downstream tasks such as remote homology identification and variant effect prediction. Demonstrating how bespoke structure and modifications were used to meet the architectural constraints over raw reads.

Zhang and Imoto (2024), performed a review analysing cases where genomic data was transformed into image based representations, such as Chaos Game Representation (CGR), Frequency CGR (FCGR), and read pileup images for input in ML pipeline, concluding that deep learning models extract more biologically meaningful features when genomic data is transformed into structured, image-based representations which are aligned to input constraints of the ML model.

These examples demonstrate a clear pattern: ML in genomics works only when the data is transformed into a format that aligns with the statistical and architectural expectations of the learning models.

Notably, none of these tools use the standard genomic formats as direct input into the ML models; instead, the initial formats were reengineered to restore structure, preserve local context, and enable learning with ML models.

1.6 - The Absence of a Standardised ML-Native Genomic Format

1.6.1 - Existing Representations: Ad Hoc Structures for ML Compatibility

While machine learning is increasingly used to perform analysis and other tasks with genomic data, there is currently no standardised data format which structurally represents genomic and epigenomic data in a way that is both reusable and aligned with the constraints of machine learning models. The lack of a standardised and unified format to address the inherent format misalignment between genomic data and native ML requirements results in researchers developing ad hoc task-specific data representations, which, even though stored in generic containers, lack a shared schema, limiting cross-study reproducibility and integration.

1.6.1.1 - Ad Hoc Structures

For example, the one-hot encoded DNA tensor is commonly used to transform nucleotide bases into a numerical representation, where each nucleotide base is represented as a four-dimensional vector. These vectors are then transformed into a matrix of fixed length where each column corresponds to one of the four nucleotide bases (Kelley et al., 2016).

K-mer token sequences are often used in transformer-based models, such as DNABERT, to transform nucleotide sequences into substrings, which capture the spatial context and semantic relationships in genomic data (Ji et al., 2021).

Previous models have also represented epigenetic features such as chromatin accessibility, histone modifications, and transcription factor binding across different cell types as multi-channel signal matrices, which were used as input to predict gene expression across the genome (Singh et al., 2016; Singh et al., 2017).

1.6.1.1 - Containers

These representations are then stored in container formats such as `.h5`, due to the format's hierarchical structure and I/O options (Folk et al., 2011); `.tfrecord`, for its native

integration with the TensorFlow application, enabling scalable data streaming and batching (Abadi et al., 2015); `.pkl`, which enables the serialisation of objects during preprocessing (Python Software Foundation, 2025); and `.txt` for human-readable data storage.

Whilst this workaround imposes an artificial structure on symbolic genomic data and can be effective for specific tasks, the resulting outputs are stored in generic data containers lacking any formal shared schema. Such a schema is required for coordinate systems, the integration of metadata, and interoperability across gene types without explicit data reengineering. This absence of a formalised, ML-native format has hindered research reproducibility and scalability in genomic medicine.

Even more structured efforts, such as converting genomic and methylation information into pixel-based formats, remain constrained by these limitations, reducing reproducibility and limiting scalability across datasets and studies.

1.6.2 - Pixel-Based Genomic Representations

Researchers have attempted to convert genomic and methylation data into pixel-based formats for compatibility with deep learning models such as convolutional neural networks. These formats aim to restructure the fragmented and incompatible genomic representations into a structured, spatially coherent layout which encodes the contextual information of biological data that CNNs require as input. However, existing approaches remain ad hoc due to their task-specificity, lack of coordinate systems and standardised schemas across cell and study type, which limits their broader use.

1.6.2.1 - Genotype Pixel Imaging (GPxl)

Albrecht-Buehler (2009) first described an image-based representation of genomic data through the Genome Pixel Imaging (GPxl) method. In this approach, the nucleotide sequences were transformed into 2D greyscale pixel images, where each pixel was represented by a greyscale value which corresponded to the nucleotide base (A, T, G, or C), which enabled the visual detection of non-random repetitive elements and structural

regularities. Using the method, Albrecht-Buehler was able to reveal a substantial prevalence of tetra-GA sequences, which occur with 4-bp periodicity.

However, GPxl was not designed for machine learning pipelines, as it did not enforce standardisation. For example, the spatial arrangement of GA-sequences was often determined by the order of their natural genomic occurrence within a chromosome, but with no alignment to a shared biological reference, coordinate system or chromosomal positions. This resulted in various spatial configurations across the images, limiting its utility in feature representation for pattern recognition in various learning models.

1.6.2.2 - SNP-Encoded CNNs

Muneeb et al. (2022) used single-nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) genotype data derived from simulated chromosome 21 data to create a 2D greyscale image for input into a two-dimensional convolutional neural network (2DCNN) for a classification task between cases and controls. Each SNP was numerically encoded with values 0–2 (aa = 0, aA/Aa = 1, and AA = 2), which preserved genotype data. In reshaping SNP matrices into fixed-size 2D arrays using p-value statistics from GWAS summary statistics, the authors were able to use the images as input to a CNN classifier, achieving an accuracy score of up to 0.824, comparable to 1DCNN models (up to 0.854).

However, similar to the GPxl method, the spatial location of the SNPs did not reflect their actual genomic positions or preserve structural relationships, which is important for biological interpretation. Furthermore, no information on chromosomal coordinates of the SNPs was encoded, and the sizing and arrangement of the SNP into the square matrices was determined solely by the p-value threshold ordering. As a result, the spatial arrangement of the SNPs varied across the samples, which undermines the consistency required by ML for effective feature learning, reducing the probability of the representation capturing a biologically meaningful pattern in the data.

1.6.2.3 - Common Limitations

These attempts to convert genomic and epigenomic data into pixel arrays, where each pixel represents a form of biological data, demonstrate the feasibility of using such formats both for human visualisation and use with machine learning architectures. However, these implementations share several limitations:

- The spatial layout of features is arbitrary and determined by the sequencing technology or design choices defined by the task;
- Only a single omic type is encoded;
- There is no standardised schema that includes a coordinate system governing the format;
- The representations lack biological positional grounding and integrated metadata.

As such, while these studies highlight the potential in using pixel-based formats for genomic and epigenomic visualisation and analysis, they remain as isolated, ad hoc, task-specific implementations rather than standardised, reusable formats which can be used for broader machine learning applications.

1.6.3 - Limitations of Current Representations: Fragmentation, Incompatibility, and No Integration

Across the various biological data representations, whether tensorized, tokenised, or visualised as pixelated images, the field of genomics lacks a reusable, interpretable, format scalable across cell and sample types, suitable for deep learning. Existing approaches are fragmented and store isolated data types without structural metadata or alignment to biological context in order to capture the spatial context and semantic relationships. Additionally, no single data representation supports the joint modelling of both nucleotide sequence and methylation percentages at CpG sites, within a unified format.

This absence of a formal ML-native format has limited the progress of multi-omic modelling, cross-study development, and scalability of clinical and molecular research using machine

learning in genomics. This field lacks a format that encodes both genomic and epigenomic data in a numerically encoded, spatially coherent, metadata-aware representation with coordinate systems scalable across cell types and compatible with deep learning architectures. These limitations directly motivate the development of a unified approach that meets these criteria.

Chapter 2 – Constraints and Problem Definition

2.1 - Constraint Overview and Motivation

Despite the technological advancements in DNA sequencing, methylation profiling, and machine learning, genomic research and clinical translation have remained constrained due to the lack of a native, universally adopted, machine learning compatible format which encodes both genomic and epigenomic data. As demonstrated in the previous section, this limitation acts as a barrier for the integration of genomic and epigenomic data, limiting the interpretability, scalability, and reproducibility of genomic and epigenomic studies.

These limitations can be characterised into eight distinct constraints, including: the lack of standardisation, the fragmentation between genomic and epigenomic data formats, and the absence of shared coordinate and metadata conventions which work across both biological domains. Together, these constraints form the foundation of this project's overarching aim and objectives. The full set of technical challenges is outlined below:

T1: Lack of standardisation

There is no widely accepted, universal schema for representing both genomic and epigenomic data in deep learning workflows, limiting reproducibility and scalability in multi-omic studies.

T2: Format fragmentation

Genomic and epigenomic data are typically stored in separate, symbolic, domain-specific formats. They are not directly interoperable without conversion, which complicates integrated analysis and introduces processing overhead.

T3: Lack of ML-native formats

Genomic and epigenomic data formats are not natively structured for direct use in deep learning. The use of these formats in ML experiments often requires ad-hoc transformations, reducing comparability and reproducibility across datasets, cell types, and experimental conditions.

T4: No unified genomic and epigenomic format

There is no single representation which natively combines both genomic and epigenomic data in a biologically coherent and structured way, which limits the understanding of multi-omic regulatory interactions.

T5: Lack of genomic and epigenomic coordinate and metadata standards

While genomic formats like BAM/CRAM capture positional and strand data, there is no consistent cross-domain standard for data interpretability, complicating the harmonisation of data sets from different genome builds, sequencing assays, and tools.

T6: Tool-specific workflows

Pipelines like *Bismark v0.23* or *GATK v4.2.2.0* (Broad Institute, 2024) produce output formats that are optimised for their respective tools. Although conversions are possible, they require tool-specific conversions for use in ML, limiting interoperability across tools and platforms.

T7: High preprocessing overhead

Preparing genomic and epigenomic data for ML often requires extensive manual preprocessing, which limits reproducibility and increases the risk of artefacts.

T8: Poor scalability of current ML formats

Most existing encodings used to translate either genomic or epigenetic data in past ML studies are bespoke and often cannot be reused across cell types and datasets, which limits generalisation and research impact.

Chapter 3 – Aims and Objectives

3.1 - Aims

To design and implement a standardised, machine learning native data format, the Omic Image Format (OIF), which encodes both genomic and epigenomic data. Specifically, it will integrate aligned nucleotide sequence and DNA methylation data into a unified, interpretable, numerically encoded format that is directly compatible with deep learning pipelines and distributed as an open-source Python package for accessibility.

3.2 - Objectives

To achieve this aim, the project defines five objectives that directly address the constraints outlined in section 7:

O1: Develop a native ML format for both genomic and epigenomic representation

Develop a reusable, numerically encoded data format which integrates nucleotide sequence, methylation information, strand orientation, and genomic coordinate metadata to meet tensor-based ML input requirements.

Addresses: T1, T2, T3, T4, T6

O2: Preserve biological structure and spatial locality in encoded outputs

Maintain the order of biological sequences, coordinate integrity, sequence quality and strand direction across encoded regions, with support for region-specific encoding and methylation-aware and methylation-unaware pipelines.

Addresses: T2, T4, T5, T7, T8

O3: Minimise manual and task-specific preprocessing for ML models

Generate fixed-size, ML-compatible output directly from aligned nucleotide sequence and methylation data, reducing or eliminating additional ad hoc transformations.

Addresses: T3, T6, T7

O4: Develop the OIF pipeline for accessibility and reproducibility

Design and implement the OIF encoding pipeline as a modular, workflow-agnostic Python package. Ensuring it supports reproducibility across datasets and compatibility with multiple machine learning frameworks by using standardised numerical encoding and metadata structures.

Addresses: T1, T6, T7, T8

O5: Publicly release the command line interface (CLI) OIF pipeline for adoption

Publish the CLI pipeline as an installable Python package via PyPI under the name *OmicImage* to support cross-platform usability, reproducibility and adoption across research groups.

Addresses: T6, T7, T8

Chapter 4 – The Omic Image Format (OIF)

4.1 - Introduction to the OIF

The Omic Image Format (OIF) is a novel bioinformatic format specifically designed for direct compatibility with machine learning pipelines. It encodes both nucleotide sequence and DNA methylation information into a single format. It addresses structural incompatibilities which currently exist across the various sequencing data formats. The data is numerically encoded and biologically structured to preserve spatial locality, which enables deep learning models to leverage the positional and contextual relationships inherent in genomic data.

4.2 - Structural Overview

Unlike genomic and epigenomic file types such as FASTQ, BAM, VCF, and IDAT, which store nucleotide sequence and DNA methylation data in fragmented formats containing both symbolic and numeric values, the OIF encodes both nucleotide sequence and DNA methylation information into a 2D image. Each pixel in the image corresponds to a specific position of a nucleotide base and associated genetic and epigenetic information.

This information is paired with a structured metadata file, which captures the unified coordinate system, ensuring both integrity and biological context.

4.2.1 - RGBA Encoding of Genomic and Epigenomic Features

Within the OIF image, each pixel consists of four channels (R, G, B, A). Each channel encodes either a genomic or epigenomic attribute (**see Figure 4.1**). Specifically:

- **R channel:** Base identity (A, C, G, T, N) mapped to greyscale values.
- **G channel:** Methylation state, scaled from CpG report values (0–255); a default value of 128 indicates no methylation data.
- **B channel:** Base quality score, scaled from Phred+33 scores (0–255).
- **A channel:** Strand orientation, binary encoded (+ or -).

This structure ensures that both the biological composition and the positional context of genomic and methylation features are preserved within each pixel, thereby enabling precise downstream analysis by machine learning models.

Figure 4.1 Example of the Omic Image Format (OIF) output. Each pixel encodes four attributes: the position and value of the nucleotide base (R channel), the associated methylation percentage (G channel), the quality score (B channel), and the orientation of the strand (A channel).

Chapter 5 – Methodology Part 1: OIF Design and Implementation

5.1 - Constraint-Driven Design and Implementation

The development of the Omic Image Format was guided by a set of critical technological and biological design constraints defined in Chapter 7. These challenges reflect the deep structural mismatches between traditional genomic and epigenomic data formats and the input requirements of deep learning pipelines. In this section, each constraint is outlined, followed by an explanation of how the Omic Image Format (OIF), encoding schema, and modular and open-source implementation explicitly address these challenges.

For clarity and traceability, each subsection includes the names of key functions and their source files within the released codebase, enabling direct correspondence between the methodological explanation and the publicly available implementation.

5.1.1 - Numerical Encoding of Genomic and Epigenomic Data

To ensure the direct ML compatibility of the format, which requires numerical, tensor-compatible input and reduces the extensive ad hoc processing otherwise needed to transform biological data into a usable numerical format, the OIF maps every nucleotide base to an 8-bit integer (A = 32, T = 96, C = 160, G = 224, and N = 255), a mapping scheme chosen for this implementation, and converts it via `nucleotide_base_to_greyscale()` (`shared.py`). The CpG methylation percentages for the corresponding bases are loaded with `load_scaled_CpG_methylation_data()` (`methylation_loader.py`) and scaled via `methylation_to_greyscale()` (`image_encoder.py`) to an 8-bit representation, defaulting to 128 if there is no methylation value for that genomic position. Phred scores from the SAM format are rescaled to 8-bit values using a maximum threshold of `40 MAX_BASE_QUALITY` (`shared.py`); strand orientation is recorded as 255 (forward) or 0 (reverse) by `check_strand()` (`shared.py`), ensuring that the channels are consistently encoded.

Next, the numerical encodings of the four channels are packaged into an RGBA list by `construct_pixel()` (`sam_parser.py`). The `insert_pixel()` (`sam_parser.py`) function writes each RGBA list to a dictionary. Once each read and its

associated genomic position have been processed, `create_rgba_array()` (`image_encoder.py`) iterates through the elements in the dictionary to create an array of shape (Row, Length, 4). Finally, `convert_rgba_array_to_image()` (`image_encoder.py`) serialises that array and writes it out as a standard PNG file. This end-to-end pipeline transforms genomic and epigenomic information into a numerically encoded format, reducing the need for additional symbolic conversion or manual reshaping of data at the ML input stage.

5.1.2 - Preserve Biological Structure and Spatial Locality in Encoded Outputs

To preserve biological spatiality and adhere to key biological constraints, such as the order of nucleotide reads and genomic coordinate information, which are essential for understanding gene regulation, chromatin accessibility, and transcriptional directionality, the OIF aligns the methylation position and nucleotide base from the SAM file and CpG methylation report. The methylation value, nucleotide base position, base quality score, and strand orientation are stored together in a single RGBA channel. This information is also stored in a TSV file, enabling the reconstruction of the RGBA image with complete retention of the biological composition and methylation values. As a result, the format produces a spatially coherent image of the sequence and maintains spatial continuity without requiring additional sorting steps.

5.1.3 - Unified Coordinate and Metadata Framework for Multi-Omic Integration

A shared coordinate and metadata system has been developed to facilitate joint modelling and representation of both genomic and epigenomic data. The OIF format performs this in the function `run_rgba_pipeline()` (`utils.py`), where the metadata, which contains the chromosome, absolute position, base, methylation value, strand, quality, and pixel coordinates, is collected into a list, which `write_read_alignment_coordinates()` (`utils.py`) then writes to a TSV file. This approach ensures that for any region of interest, both nucleotide sequence and DNA methylation data are jointly represented in a spatially aligned, ML-native format that

preserves genomic order, maintains base-level quality scores, and can be integrated with downstream tools such as interpretable ML applications and genome browser visualisation.

5.1.4 - Low Preprocessing Overhead through Automated Data Preparation

To reduce the need for extensive downstream data preprocessing when converting genomic and epigenomic data into ML-ready formats, a common barrier to reproducibility and scalability, the OIF generates ML-native images directly from pre-aligned nucleotide sequences and an optional methylation report. The pipeline accepts a SAM file, an optional CpG methylation report, and an output directory as input. Additional optional parameters include `--mapq`, and `--full-read`.

The outputs are a PNG image, a TSV, and a plain text metadata file. All transformation steps within the OIF workflow, including numerical encoding, coordinate mapping, and image construction, are handled internally by the codebase. As a result, once alignment and methylation calling have been completed upstream, no further preprocessing is required between input into the OIF pipeline and the machine learning data input stage, allowing for low preprocessing overhead through automated data preparation.

5.1.5 - Workflow-Agnostic Implementation and Interoperability

To reduce fragmentation and enable interoperability across workflows and pipelines, the OIF interface is standardised through the use of a command-line interface (`cli.py`). The complete OIF pipeline uses only platform-agnostic Python libraries, including standard libraries such as `argparse`, `os`, and `datetime`, and external libraries such as `numpy`, `Pillow (PIL)`, and `pysam`.

Additionally, the encoding schema of the pixelated output utilises built-in types and constant variables, which supports workflow agnosticism. The modular design accommodates diverse pipelines while avoiding the rigidity of traditional symbolic formats. The outputs, generated by `convert_rgba_array_to_image()` (`image_encoder.py`) and `write_read_alignment_coordinates()` (`utils.py`), consist of a PNG image

and TSV metadata file, both of which are directly compatible with ML frameworks such as PyTorch, TensorFlow, and JAX, reducing the need for custom parsers or preprocessing beyond the ML input stage.

5.1.6- An Open-source Pipeline for Accessibility and Reproducibility

To facilitate accessibility, interoperability, and reproducibility across research groups and studies, we developed and publicly released *OmicImage*, an open-source Python package which implements the OIF pipeline. The package is available via the Python Package Index (PyPI) and can be installed with the command: `pip install OmicImage`

In most environments, installation of the package requires minimal configuration, and the package can be integrated into existing bioinformatics workflows without modifying the underlying code. By publishing the OIF pipeline as an installable package, its execution can be standardised across different environments, studies, and research groups, supporting reproducibility and accessibility.

Chapter 6 – Methodology Part 2: Evaluation and Verification Approach

6.1 - Evaluation Methodology

The objective of this evaluation was to verify that the OIF pipeline correctly encodes aligned DNA nucleotide reads and associated DNA methylation data into a four-channel PNG image and a per-pixel coordinate TSV metadata file.

6.1.1 - Verification Approach

To validate the integrity of the RGBA values and the positional consistency of the encoded bases, the evaluation consisted of two sequential tests:

PNG-to-TSV RGBA Consistency Test

This test validated per-pixel RGBA values in the PNG image against corresponding values recorded in the TSV metadata file. The values in each RGBA channel of the PNG image were extracted using the Pillow library and compared against the corresponding RGBA values recorded in the TSV metadata for the same pixel coordinates. This step confirmed that the image writing process accurately preserves data between the OIF and TSV metadata file.

TSV-to-SAM and CpG Report Distribution Consistency Test

This test assessed whether the genomic position and associated methylation value recorded in the TSV file matched those in the original SAM file and CpG methylation report. Using the TSV metadata, the counts and percentages for each encoded base, strand orientation, and methylation position and value were calculated to generate summary statistics which described locational properties associated with each encoded base, the distribution of the strand, and the methylation frequency. These metrics, derived independently from both the SAM file and the CpG methylation report, were used to confirm whether the encoding process maintained the genomic positions of reads and accurately reflected both the position and percentages of methylation values from the original CpG methylation report.

6.1.2 - Metrics

Using the output from the verification steps described in 6.1.1, the following quantitative metrics were calculated:

- **Channel Match Rate** - The percentage of pixels where the value in each RGBA channel of the PNG image exactly matches the corresponding value recorded in the TSV metadata file at the same pixel coordinates.
- **Genomic Position Match Rate** - The percentage of base positions in the TSV metadata file that exactly match the corresponding position in the SAM file.
- **Methylation Position Match Rate** - The percentage of methylation sites in the TSV metadata file that exactly match the corresponding position in the CpG methylation file.
- **Strand Orientation Match Rate** - The percentage of strand orientations (+ or -) in the TSV metadata file that match those in the SAM file.
- **Methylation Value Match Rate** - The percentage of positions where the methylation value in the TSV metadata exactly matches the value in the CpG methylation report.

6.2 - Dataset

The experimental validation of the Omic Image Format (OIF) utilised the *Komagataella phaffii* genome assembly (GCA_900235035.2, strain CBS 7435), obtained from the NCBI Genome Database. This organism was selected due to the genome being well annotated, its relatively small genome size, and its widespread use as a reference strain in bioinformatic and genomic studies.

6.3 - Experimental Setup

Before conversion using the OIF pipeline, nucleotide reads were aligned to the *Komagataella phaffii* reference genome (GCA_900235035.2, strain CBS 7435) using *minimap2* v2.26 (Li 2018) with default parameters. *Bismark* v0.23 (Krueger and Andrews 2011) was then used to generate the CpG methylation reports. Alignment files were stored in SAM format, and methylation calls were stored in CpG methylation report format.

6.3.1 - Pipeline Execution

The OIF pipeline was executed via the command line, calling the script `build_rgba_methylation.py`, which encodes both nucleotide base and methylation data into the OIF.

Parameters included in pipeline execution:

- **Required:** Coordinate-sorted SAM file containing aligned reads to the *Komagataella phaffii* reference genome (GCA_900235035.2, strain CBS 7435), and the parameter `--width 1300` to set the horizontal width of the generated image.
- **Optional:** CpG methylation report file.

Parameters omitted from pipeline execution (resulting in default values):

- `--full-read`: Only the first base of each aligned read was encoded rather than every base.
- `--mapq`: No minimum mapping quality filter was applied to the nucleotide base.

Outputs from pipeline execution were:

- **PNG image** representing genomic and epigenomic data encoded in the OIF.
- **TSV metadata file** containing the per-pixel annotations (chromosome, position, base, methylation value, strand, quality, and pixel coordinates) of each nucleotide read.
- **Metadata file** containing the final width and height of the RGBA image.

Chapter 7 – Results

7.1 - Overview

The Omic Image Format (OIF) was evaluated to validate the ability of the encoding pipeline to preserve both the positional consistency and contextual integrity of the nucleotide and methylation attributes from the SAM file and CpG methylation report.

7.2 - Channel Match Rates

The channel match rate across the four RGBA channels showed exact matches with the entries in the TSV file. Contextual information of the nucleotide base, methylation status of the corresponding base, the base quality score, and the orientation of the strand, all achieved 100% match rates (**Table 7.1**).

Table 7.1: RGBA channel match rates

Channel	Attribute	Total Pixels Checked	Matches	Match Rate (%)
R	Base Identity	1330388	1330388	100.0
G	Methylation Value	1330388	1330388	100.0
B	Base Quality Score	1330388	1330388	100.0
A	Strand Orientation	1330388	1330388	100.0

Table 7.1: RGBA channel match rate. Summary of match rates for each RGBA channel, comparing pixel values in the PNG image with the corresponding entries in the TSV metadata file.

7.3 - Base Position and Strand Orientation Consistency

Comparing the position of each nucleotide base in the TSV file against the corresponding values in the SAM file, the analysis demonstrated full positional consistency (100.00%). Similarly, the distribution consistency of the strand orientation information was 100.00% **(Table 7.2)**.

Table 7.2 – Base Position and Strand Orientation Consistency

Metric	Total nucleotide records in TSV File	Number of Matches	Match Rate (%)
Base Position Consistency (TSV vs SAM)	1330388	1330388	100.0
Strand Orientation Consistency (TSV vs SAM)	1330388	1330388	100.0

Table 7.2: Base Position and Strand Orientation Consistency. Match rates for base position and strand orientation between the TSV metadata file and the SAM file.

7.4 - Methylation Data Representation

To evaluate the encoding of methylation information in the Omic Image Format, a comparison was performed between the genomic coordinates and methylation values in the encoded TSV file and those in the CpG methylation report. Of the 1,330,388 total entries in the TSV file, 53,768 (4.04%) contained methylation values, which indicated they were methylated.

All 53,768 methylated positions in the TSV file matched genomic positions listed in the CpG methylation report. Among these matched sites, 49,246 positions (91.59%) had methylation values that exactly matched the CpG methylation report (**Table 7.3**).

Table 7.3 – Methylation Data Representation

Metric	Count	% of Total TSV Entries	% of Methylated TSV Positions
Total TSV Records	1330388	100.00%	–
TSV Methylated Positions	53,768	4.04%	100.00%
Matched CpG Report Positions (Methylation Positional Match Rate)	53,768	4.04%	100.00%
Exact Value Matches with CpG (Methylation Value Match Rate)	49,246	3.70%	91.59%

Table 7.3: Methylation Data Representation. Counts and match rates for methylated positions in the TSV file, including methylation position, and value match rates with the CpG methylation report.

7.5- Methylation Error Analysis

To investigate this discrepancy, a tolerance of ± 5 in methylation value was applied to account for minor rounding differences. This adjustment yielded 53,409 matches, corresponding to a match rate of 99.33%, confirming that most mismatches resulted from rounding during encoding (**Table 7.4**).

Table 7.4 – Methylation Match After ± 5 Tolerance - Error Analysis

Metric	Count	Match Rate (%)
Matches After ± 5 Tolerance (Methylation Value Match Rate)	53,409	99.33%

Table 7.4: Methylation Match After ± 5 Tolerance. Match rates for methylation values in the TSV file and CpG methylation report after applying a ± 5 tolerance to account for rounding differences.

Chapter 8 – Discussion

8.1 - Integrating Biological, Clinical, and Computational Context

This study aimed to introduce and address a fundamental barrier to the progression of genomic medicine: the lack of a genomic data format which encodes both genomic and epigenomic data in an ML-native format.

As established in earlier chapters, the function of a gene product is determined not only by nucleotide sequences but also by the epigenetic layer, which governs when, where, and how much a gene is expressed (Hotchkiss, 1948; Allfrey et al., 1964; Esteller, 2007).

However, analysis of either layer is constrained by existing genomic formats such as FASTQ, BAM, and VCF, and epigenomic formats such as IDAT and methylation reports, which are structurally incompatible with one another (Hayes et al., 2024; Duan et al., 2021). These formats often require bespoke, ad hoc transformations for machine learning (Zhou and Troyanskaya, 2015; Avsec et al., 2021) and lack a unified coordinate and metadata system (Chen et al., 2020). Together, these computational limitations reduce reproducibility and limit scalability across datasets and studies. The Omic Image Format (OIF) is introduced as a direct response to these constraints.

8.2 - Interpretation of Encoding Performance

The PNG-to-TSV RGBA Consistency test achieved an exact channel match rate of 100% across all four channels, demonstrating that contextual genetic and epigenetic data are aligned and preserved between the OIF and TSV metadata file.

In the TSV-to-SAM and CpG Report Distribution Consistency test, the RGBA format achieved a base composition and strand distribution consistency rate of 100%, demonstrating that the TSV and OIF preserve biological position and context. Additionally, the positional match of methylation sites was 100%, confirming that the OIF encoding accurately aligns and preserves methylation calls in both the OIF and TSV metadata file.

For methylation values, direct comparison with the CpG methylation report yielded a 91.59% match rate, which increased to 99.33% after applying a ± 5 tolerance to account for

rounding. This indicates that most mismatches result from converting methylation values into the 0–255 range during the encoding process. These findings demonstrate that the Omic Image Format preserves methylation values with high accuracy once rounding effects are considered.

Collectively, the channel match rate, genomic and methylation position match rate, and strand orientation match rate of 100%, along with a methylation value match rate of 99.33%, demonstrate that the Omic Image Format encodes both genomic and DNA methylation data with high accuracy.

8.3 - Clinical and Diagnostic Implications

By unifying sequence and methylation data in a single representation and providing an ML native data format, the OIF directly addresses the structural challenges highlighted in 1.5.2. The mismatch between ML architectures and the data formats used in genomic and epigenomic sequencing has hindered the feasibility of large-scale ML experiments in this domain. In the absence of a native ML format, researchers must rely on custom, task-specific preprocessing pipelines, adding computational overhead and introducing variability, which reduces reproducibility and limits scalability across datasets and studies.

The OIF's ability to integrate both DNA sequence and methylation information could support the development of diagnostic tools capable of distinguishing hereditary from sporadic disease. If successfully translated into clinical workflows, this improves both risk assessment and family screening. Additionally, the OIF can enable researchers to perform ML-based experiments in a reproducible and scalable way.

Machine learning has demonstrated a transformative impact in healthcare. For example, ML models have been created that can identify cancer subtypes from gene expression data (Divite et al., 2022) and detect diabetic retinopathy from retinal images (Gulshan, 2016).

In both cases, the image-based representation met the structural requirements of ML architectures, allowing for the accurate representation of the underlying data. Prior to this work, no publicly available format and translational tool existed for encoding both genomic

and epigenomic data into an ML-native format. By providing both the format and the encoding tool, the OIF enables genomic and epigenetic studies to be conducted at scale.

8.4 - Computational Integration and Multi-Omic Scalability

The results of the evaluation suggest that a primary barrier to integrated analysis has been the incompatibility of genomic and epigenomic formats, and not the inherent complexity of the biological samples. The OIF has fulfilled all five objectives outlined in 1.5 (O1–O5) by:

- Created a novel unified ML-native genomic–epigenomic format (**Addresses: O1**).
- Preserved biological composition and spatial integrity (**Addresses: O2**).
- Eliminated the need for ad hoc preprocessing (**Addresses: O3**).
- Developed a novel workflow-agnostic encoding pipeline (**Addresses: O4**).
- Released the open-source implementation for global adoption (**Addresses: O5**).

Rather than replacing domain-specific non-interoperable formats such as *Bismark's* CpG methylation reports or *GATK's* VCFs, the OIF complements them by providing an ML-ready image-based representation of their outputs. This reduces preprocessing overhead, improves reproducibility, and enables joint modelling without extensive data harmonisation reported as a bottleneck in multi-omic cancer subtyping (Duan et al., 2021) and cross-domain genomic integration (Hayes et al., 2024).

Chapter 9 – Conclusion

9.1 - A Unified Approach

This study presents the Omic Image Format (OIF), a unified, machine-learning–native representation for genomic and epigenomic data. By numerically encoding both nucleotide sequence and methylation state into a spatially coherent image with associated metadata, the OIF resolves long-standing barriers to multi-omic integration, reproducibility, and ML compatibility.

The evaluation demonstrates that OIF maintains positional and compositional values across both genomic and epigenomic layers, preserving 100% of the biological coordinates of genomic and methylation data, whilst preserving methylation values in over 99.33% of cases with standard CpG methylation reports. By aligning biological features with ML architecture requirements, OIF has the potential to accelerate research, improve diagnostic workflows, and advance the integration of genomics and epigenomics into precision medicine.

9.2 - Future Directions

Future work should transform DNA and methylation sequencing data from rare and inherited diseases such as ADPKD, ALS, β -thalassemia, and DCM into the Omic Image Format for use as training data in deep learning studies. In these diseases, up to 40% of cases can be attributed to genetic variants. This low yield has been compounded by the absence of a unifying ML-native format for machine learning. OIF removes this barrier, allowing for integrated multi-omic analyses. Such studies could improve disease subtype classification, resolve idiopathic cases, and further our understanding of human disease, ultimately leading to better clinical outcomes.

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